

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**HEALTH AWARENESS OF INFLUENZA IN THE COMMUNITY
OF AL-BAHA REGION****Dr. Mohammed Saleh Almane Alghamdi, Dr. Mohammed Yaanallah Mohammed
Alghamdi, Dr. Abdulrahman Naji Salem Alzahrani, Dr. Osama Abdulhadi Ali Alzahrani.****Article Received:** November 2022 **Accepted:** November 2022 **Published:** December 2022**Abstract:**

Flu awareness helps with the importance of preventing influenza, and thus maintaining the health of the community. It is a viral infection of the lungs and airways with an influenza virus. It causes fever, runny nose, sore throat, cough, headache, muscle aches, and a general feeling of illness (malaise).

A cross-sectional web survey was introduced to the residents of Albaha region and the questionnaire contains sections focused on participants' socio-demographic, different.

Our survey concluded that respondents generally have awareness of influenza except for some information that needs awareness. Media and print media including the Internet will become an important source of health care promotion.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Mohammed Saleh Almane Alghamdi,
(Forensic Consultant). Profile Number: 13JM0035081
E-mail: msalgamadi@moh.gov.sa Tel.:
00966592553331

QR code

Please cite this article in press Mohammed Saleh Almane Alghamdi et al, **Health Awareness Of Influenza In The Community Of Al-Baha Region.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2022; 09(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Flu awareness helps with the importance of preventing influenza, and thus maintaining the health of the community.

Justification:

Evaluation of the importance of community health education in Al-Baha region regarding influenza.

Objectives of the Research:

Determine the degree of importance of adherence to prevention and vaccination.

Research Methods

- Study design
- Cross –sectional analytic study prospective
- Study area: Al-Baha Region
- Sample size: 200 sample in AlBaha city
- Data collection: A structured questionnaire will be developed particularly for the purpose of this study in Arabic and also translated to English

Analysis procedure:

The analysis was primarily descriptive in nature and will perform by using SPSS program for windows.

Ethical consideration:

Permission will be taken. Data collection: Data collection will be (Arabic questionnaire).

Problem statement:

Educating the community about the importance of influenza prevention will lead to a decrease in the spread of the disease.

Rational:

Some flu patients have a lack of awareness of the disease.

Research questions:

- What is the level of awareness of influenza in the community of Al-Baha region?
- Does awareness of the long-term complications of the disease reduce their occurrence?

Hypotheses:

Awareness of the disease helps limit its spread.

Research timeframe									
Research Project	30 Days								
Develop Research Proposal									
Ask for permission to access to Statistics									
Correspondent Statistics department									
Bring statistic from statistical department									
Administer instrument(s)									
Ongoing data collection and analysis									
Final collection of data									
Research Report									

1 Month

Abstract Introduction:

It is a viral infection of the lungs and airways with an influenza virus. It causes fever, runny nose, sore throat, cough, headache, muscle aches, and a general feeling of illness (malaise).

METHODOLOGY:

A cross-sectional web survey was introduced to the residents of Albaha region.

The questionnaire contains sections focused on participants' socio-demographic, different.

RESULTS:

A total of 200 questionnaires were completed:

Percentage of women with knowledge of the first signs of breast cancer: 53.5%

Percentage of women unaware of the initial signs of breast cancer: 46.5%

The percentage of those who took the vaccine: 64.5%.

The percentage of those who did not take the vaccine is 35.5%.

The percentage of those infected after taking the vaccine: 13.5%
The percentage of those who were not infected after taking the vaccine: 86.5%

CONCLUSION:

Our survey concluded that respondents generally have awareness of influenza except for some information that needs awareness. Media and print media including the Internet will become an important source of health care promotion.

REFERENCES:

- <https://www.moh.gov.sa/HealthAwareness/EducationalContent/Diseases/Infectious/Pages/flu.aspx>
- <https://www.mayoclinic.org/ar/diseases-conditions/flu/symptoms-causes/syc-20351719>